

PURCHASE DECISION OF CONSUMERS TOWARDS BRANDED APPARELS

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Abstract:

This paper aims to make a comprehensive review of factors affecting purchaser decision towards branded apparel products. Research studies concerned with factors having impact on purchase decision of consumers towards branded apparels were reviewed. These factors include different brand, time, quality, innovativeness aspects were reported.

Key Words: Purchase Decision, Branded Apparels & Innovativeness

Introduction:

The purchase of any product by an individual is influenced by several factors including high value towards the brands, information about the products, purchase out of habit, based on experiments with the products apart from this there are several internal and external factors that determine buying forces such as needs, past experiences, personality, learning and attitudes termed as internal factors and social, marketing, and situational influences are external factors. The behaviour of the consumers varies with respect to the products they are intended to purchase (Belch & Belch, 2010).

Review of Literature:

(Rajput et al, 2012) A clear understanding of preferences of consumers will help the marketer to attract and maintain their target consumer group in better way. Price, fitting, income level of consumers are significant factors and some factors which are found to be insignificant are status, durability, and celebrity endorsement, can be ignored by the apparel retailers in their efforts to tap and capture the market.

Mittal & Aggarwal, (2012); Pandian et al, (2012); Kanthi & Kumar, (2013), The customers purchase readymade garments mostly during discount period. Price, Quality and design are the important factors considered by them while shopping.

Need for the Study:

Many developments and changes are taking place around us with all the industries and firms within each industry including garment industry with an intention to keep pace with the changes and diverse needs of the people. Though for decades together, marketers have regarded "consumer" as the king and evolved all activities to satisfy him, this concept is gaining more momentum and importance today. This can largely be attributed to the prevailing market situation. Not only competition has become intense but over and above with the market being flooded with many products. The challenge before the marketers is to understand the diversity of consumer behaviour and offer goods and services accordingly (Nair, 2004). Understanding the reasons for studying a discipline enables one to better appreciate its contributions. Studying consumer behaviour has a lot of benefits to marketers that enable them to create long lasting relationship with customers. With that concern the researcher involves in identifying the decision of consumers in the purchase of branded apparels.

Research Objective of the Study:

Purchase decision is facilitated by having a comprehensive knowledge of the brand which helps in evoking positive effects towards the brand, as these days people don't buy the product they buy images (brands). It influences brand choice, preferences and intention to purchase of consumers. The objective of the study is to analyze the significance of demographic profile of consumers affecting the purchase decision of branded apparels.

Sample Size:

Determining the size of sample that is needed for a particular piece of research. For this research paper 384 sample size is taken for the interviews.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Factor analysis:

The key concept of factor analysis is that multiple observed variables have similar patterns of responses because they are all associated with a latent (i.e. not directly measured) variable.

The below table indicates that KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy test is significant (because the test value is greater than 0.700 at 0.749) and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is also found to be significant (approx. Chi-square = 15551.608, df = 1485, Significance 0.000). This indicates that the dataset is fit to perform factor analysis. Varimax Rotation Technique is used to examine the obtained factors, and all item loadings above 0.50 are considered for the scale in factor analysis.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.749
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	15551.608
	df	1485
	Sig.	.000

Initial communalities are the estimates of the variance in each variable accounted for by all the components or factors. For Principal components extraction, this is always equal to 1 for correlation analysis. Extraction communalities are the estimates of the variance in each variable accounted for by the component.

Communalities		
Description of Variables	Initial	Extraction
All brands are the same in overall quality	1.000	.570
The most well-known national brands are the best for me	1.000	.663
Shopping in store is a waste of my time	1.000	.645
My standards and expectations for products I buy are very high	1.000	.621
Highly advertised brands are usually very good	1.000	.457
I carefully watch how much money I spend	1.000	.549
I make my shopping trips fast	1.000	.645
I keep my wardrobe up-to-date with the changing fashions	1.000	.603
I should plan my shopping more carefully than I do	1.000	.682
I stay on top of trends and fashion	1.000	.465
I usually chose lower price products	1.000	.653
A brand recommended in a consumer magazine is an excellent choice for me	1.000	.466
I cannot choose products by myself (I need help)	1.000	.380
Expensive brands are usually the best	1.000	.209
It is fun to buy something new and exciting	1.000	.394
I enjoy shopping just for the fun of it	1.000	.475
I usually compare advertisements when buying fashionable products.	1.000	.457
The more recognizable the brand, the better the quality of the product	1.000	.356
I consider price first, when making purchases	1.000	.479
I make a special effort to choose high quality products	1.000	.492
I am impulsive when making purchases	1.000	.509
I usually compare at least three brands before choosing	1.000	.400
I accept that top quality products are much more expensive than regular quality products	1.000	.513
I usually buy well-known, national, or designer brands	1.000	.566
I usually choose the most expensive brands	1.000	.575
I get most of the information about products online	1.000	.487
When it comes to purchasing products, I try to get the very best or perfect choice	1.000	.607
I do most of my shopping on-line since it saves me time and money	1.000	.461
I buy high quality products. Since they last longer	1.000	.657
When I go to a restaurant, I feel it is safer to order dishes I am familiar with	1.000	.706
Only those products unavailable in other country should be imported	1.000	.773
The most expensive brands are usually my preferred choice	1.000	.728
All the information I get on different products confuses me	1.000	.658
I often make careless purchases that I later regret	1.000	.527
I think of myself as a brand-loyal consumer	1.000	.689
We should buy from foreign countries only those products which we cannot obtain within our own country	1.000	.641
I always make my purchases by comparing the price to the quality of the product	1.000	.702
There are too many brands to choose from so I often feel confused	1.000	.651
I take part in loyalty programmes to get discount and special deals	1.000	.437
I would rather stick with a brand I usually buy than try something I am not very sure of	1.000	.620
Sometimes it's hard to choose at which stores to shop	1.000	.152
Purchasing foreign-made products in anti- CHN/SLO/CRO	1.000	.377

should not by foreign products, because this hurts business and causes unemployment	1.000	.301
I am prone to buying items on sale or in special deals	1.000	.514
I like together as much information about a new/unfamiliar product before buying it	1.000	.489
A real Indian should always buy Indian products	1.000	.502
consumer who purchase products made in other countries are responsible for putting their fellow people out of work	1.000	.446
I am very cautious in trying new and different products	1.000	.465
I like to consult with friends and family before purchasing a product	1.000	.190
If I like a brand, I rarely switch from it just to try something new	1.000	.385
We should purchase products manufactured instead of letting other countries get rich from us	1.000	.366
It may cost me in the long run, but I prefer to buy other country - made products	1.000	.357
I rarely buy brands about which I am uncertain how they will perform	1.000	.343
When I see a new brand on the shelf, I am not afraid of giving it a try	1.000	.311
I take the time to shop carefully for best buys	1.000	.383
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Only those components are considered as principal components which have an eigen value greater than 1. Here, the first six components have an eigen value of more than 1, which explains 72.966% of total variance, and the remaining components explain 27.034% of total variance. The below table presents the total variance of the observed variables explained by each of the principal components / factors. For arriving at possible factors from total 55 variables, rotation was converged in 17 iterations through Varimax Rotation Technique.

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.001	20.002	20.002	11.001	20.002	20.002	6.533	11.879	11.879
2	6.153	11.187	31.189	6.153	11.187	31.189	5.262	9.568	21.447
3	3.483	6.332	37.521	3.483	6.332	37.521	5.054	9.190	30.637
4	3.193	5.806	43.327	3.193	5.806	43.327	4.480	8.146	38.783
5	1.987	3.613	46.939	1.987	3.613	46.939	4.290	7.800	46.583
6	1.932	3.513	50.453	1.932	3.513	50.453	2.128	3.870	50.453
7	1.814	3.298	53.751						
8	1.748	3.178	56.929						
9	1.575	2.864	59.792						
10	1.466	2.665	62.457						
11	1.310	2.383	64.840						
12	1.251	2.275	67.115						
13	1.140	2.073	69.188						
14	1.065	1.937	71.125						
15	1.012	1.840	72.966						
16	.949	1.725	74.691						
17	.874	1.590	76.280						
18	.870	1.582	77.862						
19	.811	1.475	79.337						
20	.728	1.324	80.660						
21	.692	1.258	81.918						
22	.671	1.220	83.138						
23	.622	1.132	84.270						
24	.592	1.077	85.347						
25	.562	1.021	86.368						
26	.535	.972	87.341						
27	.517	.941	88.281						
28	.501	.911	89.192						
29	.475	.863	90.055						

30	.451	.819	90.875						
31	.434	.789	91.663						
32	.426	.774	92.438						
33	.398	.723	93.161						
34	.371	.674	93.834						
35	.344	.625	94.459						
36	.322	.585	95.044						
37	.306	.557	95.601						
38	.293	.533	96.134						
39	.252	.458	96.592						
40	.244	.444	97.037						
41	.225	.410	97.447						
42	.204	.371	97.818						
43	.181	.330	98.148						
44	.155	.281	98.429						
45	.128	.233	98.662						
46	.121	.220	98.881						
47	.107	.194	99.076						
48	.096	.174	99.250						
49	.087	.158	99.408						
50	.076	.138	99.546						
51	.067	.121	99.667						
52	.064	.117	99.784						
53	.054	.098	99.882						
54	.038	.070	99.952						
55	.026	.048	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Short Description of Variables		Factor Loadings	Labeled as
PD12	A brand recommended in a consumer magazine is an excellent choice for me	0.619	Decision making factors with respect to brand 11.879%
PD2	The most well-known national brands are the best for me	0.715	
PD18	The more recognizable the brand, the better the quality of the product	0.581	
PD17	I usually compare advertisements when buying fashionable products.	0.631	
PD14	Expensive brands are usually the best	NR	
PD1	All brands are the same in overall quality	0.587	
PD25	I usually choose the most expensive brands	0.732	
PD16	I enjoy shopping just for the fun of it	0.647	Decision making factors with respect to time 21.447%
PD8	I keep my wardrobe up-to-date with the changing fashions	0.642	
PD3	Shopping in store is a waste of my time	0.566	
PD13	I cannot choose products by myself (I need help)	0.553	
PD7	I make my shopping trips fast	0.716	
PD21	I am impulsive when making purchases	0.666	
PD10	I stay on top of trends and fashion	0.571	
PD28	I do most of my shopping on-line since it saves me time and money	0.611	Decision making factors with respect to Quality Consciousness 30.637%
PD4	My standards and expectations for products I buy are very high	0.756	
PD20	I make a special effort to choose high quality products	0.666	
PD24	I usually buy well-known, national, or designer brands	0.638	
PD27	When it comes to purchasing products, I try to get the very best or perfect choice	0.760	
PD15	It is fun to buy something new and exciting	0.598	
PD9	I should plan my shopping more carefully than I do	0.619	
PD29	I buy high quality products. Since they last longer	0.800	
PD23	I accept that top quality products are much more expensive than	0.648	

	regular quality products		
PD6	I carefully watch how much money I spend	0.619	Decision making with respect to Price consciousness 38.783%
PD19	I consider price first, when making purchases	0.630	
PD11	I usually chose lower price products	0.648	
PD22	I usually compare at least three brands before choosing	0.536	
PD32	The most expensive brands are usually my preferred choice	0.805	
PD37	I always make my purchases by comparing the price to the quality of the product	0.642	
PD44	I am prone to buying items on sale or in special deals	0.694	Decision making with respect to information utilization 46.583%
PD33	All the information I get on different products confuses me	0.746	
PD38	There are too many brands to choose from so I often feel confused	0.611	
PD34	I often make careless purchases that I later regret	0.560	
PD45	I like together as much information about a new/unfamiliar product before buying it	0.662	
PD26	I get most of the information about products online	0.592	
PD40	I would rather stick with a brand I usually buy than try something I am not very sure of	0.611	Decision making with respect to Consumer innovativeness and ethnocentrism 50.453%
PD35	I think of myself as a brand-loyal consumer	0.653	
PD48	I am very cautious in trying new and different products	0.639	
PD30	When I go to a restaurant, I feel it is safer to order dishes I am familiar with	0.824	
PD31	Only those products unavailable in other country should be imported	0.833	
PD51	We should purchase products manufactured instead of letting other countries get rich from us	0.581	
PD46	A real Indian should always buy Indian products	0.582	50.453%
PD36	We should buy from foreign countries only those products which we cannot obtain within our own country	0.642	

PD5 - Highly advertised brands are usually very good, PD14 - Expensive brands are usually the best, PD39 - I take part in loyalty programmes to get discount and special deals, PD41 - Sometimes it's hard to choose at which stores to shop, PD42 - Purchasing foreign-made products in anti- CHN/SLO/CRO, PD43 -should not by foreign products, because this hurts business and causes unemployment, PD47 - consumer who purchase products made in other countries are responsible for putting their fellow people out of work, PD49 - I like to consult with friends and family before purchasing a product, PD50 - If I like a brand, I rarely switch from it just to try something new, PD52 - It may cost me in the long run, but I prefer to buy other country - made products, PD53 - I rarely buy brands about which I am uncertain how they will perform, PD54 - When I see a new brand on the shelf, I am not afraid of giving it a try, PD 55 - I take the time to shop carefully for best buys factors are not rotated.

Factor 1 – Decision making factors with respect to brand: PD12- A brand recommended in a consumer magazine is an excellent choice for me, PD2 - The most well-known national brands are the best for me, PD18 - The more recognizable the brand, the better the quality of the product, PD17 - I usually compare advertisements when buying fashionable products, PD14 - Expensive brands are usually the best, PD1 - All brands are the same in overall quality and PD25 - I usually choose the most expensive brands constitute factor I with 11.879 %.

Factor 2 - Decision making with respect to time: PD16 - I enjoy shopping just for the fun of it, PD8 - I keep my wardrobe up-to-date with the changing fashions, PD3- Shopping in store is a waste of my time, PD13 - I cannot choose products by myself (I need help), PD7 - I make my shopping trips fast, PD21 - I am impulsive when making purchases, PD10 - I stay on top of trends and fashion and PD28 - I do most of my shopping on-line since it saves me time and money constitute factor II with 21.447%.

Factor 3 – Decision making with respect to Quality consciousness: PD4 - My standards and expectations for products I buy are very high, PD20 -I make a special effort to choose high quality products, PD24 - I usually buy well-known, national, or designer brands, PD27 - When it comes to purchasing products, I try to get the very best or perfect choice, PD15 - It is fun to buy something new and exciting, PD9 - I should plan my shopping more carefully than I do, PD29 - I buy high quality products. Since they last longer and PD23 - I accept that top quality products are much more expensive than regular quality products constitute factor III with 30.637%.

Factor 4 – Decision making with respect to Price consciousness: PD 6 - I carefully watch how much money I spend, PD19 - I consider price first, when making purchases, PD11 - I usually chose lower price products, PD22 - I usually compare at least three brands before choosing, PD32 - The most expensive brands are usually my

preferred choice, PD37 - I always make my purchases by comparing the price to the quality of the product, PD44 - I am prone to buying items on sale or in special deals constitute factor IV with 38.783%.

Factor 5 – Decision making with respect to Information utilization: PD33 -All the information I get on different products confuses me, PD38 - There are too many brands to choose from so I often feel confused, PD 34 - I often make careless purchases that I later regret, PD 45 - I like together as much information about a new/unfamiliar product before buying it, PD26 - I get most of the information about products online constitute factor V with 46.583%.

Factor 6 – Decision making with respect to consumer innovativeness and Ethnocentrism: PD40 - I would rather stick with a brand I usually buy than try something I am not very sure of, PD35 - I think of myself as a brand-loyal consumer, PD48 - I am very cautious in trying new and different products, PD30 - When I go to a restaurant, I feel it is safer to order dishes I am familiar with, PD31 - Only those products unavailable in other country should be imported, PD51 - We should purchase products manufactured instead of letting other countries get rich from us, PD46 - A real Indian should always buy Indian products, PD36 - We should buy from foreign countries only those products which we cannot obtain within our own country constitute factor VI with 50.453%.

Analysis of Variance:

The factor groups of purchase decisions are tested with type of branded clothes chosen by men and women in order to test the significant difference.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between purchase decision factors and type of Indian brands preferred.

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Brand	Between Groups	3.077	4	.769	1.927	.105	NS
	Within Groups	151.273	379	.399			
	Total	154.351	383				
Time	Between Groups	2.601	4	.650	1.610	.171	NS
	Within Groups	153.070	379	.404			
	Total	155.672	383				
Quality Consciousness	Between Groups	2.074	4	.519	1.427	.224	NS
	Within Groups	137.765	379	.363			
	Total	139.839	383				
Price Consciousness	Between Groups	2.446	4	.611	1.484	.206	NS
	Within Groups	156.116	379	.412			
	Total	158.562	383				
Information Utilization	Between Groups	2.191	4	.548	1.143	.336	NS
	Within Groups	181.598	379	.479			
	Total	183.790	383				
Consumer Innovativeness and ethnocentrism	Between Groups	2.174	4	.543	1.154	.331	NS
	Within Groups	178.503	379	.471			
	Total	180.677	383				

From the table, it can be inferred that the purchase decision factors do not have significant difference with type of Indian brands preferred.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between purchase decision factors and type of International brands preferred.

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Brand	Between Groups	.916	4	.229	.565	.688	NS
	Within Groups	153.435	379	.405			
	Total	154.351	383				
Time	Between Groups	.401	4	.100	.245	.913	NS
	Within Groups	155.271	379	.410			
	Total	155.672	383				
Quality Consciousness	Between Groups	1.297	4	.324	.887	.472	NS
	Within Groups	138.542	379	.366			
	Total	139.839	383				
Price Consciousness	Between Groups	.717	4	.179	.431	.786	NS
	Within Groups	157.845	379	.416			
	Total	158.562	383				
Information Utilization	Between Groups	2.421	4	.605	1.265	.283	NS
	Within Groups	181.369	379	.479			

	Total	183.790	383				
Consumer Innovativeness and ethnocentrism	Between Groups	1.415	4	.354	.748	.560	NS
	Within Groups	179.262	379	.473			
	Total	180.677	383				

From the table, it can be inferred that the purchase decision factors do not have significant difference with type of International brands preferred.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between purchase decision factors and type of branded clothes chosen by Men.

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Brand	Between Groups	2.750	6	.458	1.140	.338	NS
	Within Groups	151.601	377	.402			
	Total	154.351	383				
Time	Between Groups	1.730	6	.288	.706	.645	NS
	Within Groups	153.941	377	.408			
	Total	155.672	383				
Quality Consciousness	Between Groups	1.277	6	.213	.579	.747	NS
	Within Groups	138.563	377	.368			
	Total	139.839	383				
Price Consciousness	Between Groups	1.972	6	.329	.791	.577	NS
	Within Groups	156.590	377	.415			
	Total	158.562	383				
Information Utilization	Between Groups	5.602	6	.934	1.975	.068	NS
	Within Groups	178.188	377	.473			
	Total	183.790	383				
Consumer Innovativeness and ethnocentrism	Between Groups	5.156	6	.859	1.846	.089	NS
	Within Groups	175.521	377	.466			
	Total	180.677	383				

From the table, it can be inferred that the purchase decision factors do not have significant difference with type of branded clothes chosen by Men.

H₀ : There is no significant difference between purchase decision factors and type of branded clothes chosen by women.

Source of Variance		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Result
Brand	Between Groups	2.156	6	.359	.890	.502	NS
	Within Groups	152.194	377	.404			
	Total	154.351	383				
Time	Between Groups	3.498	6	.583	1.444	.197	NS
	Within Groups	152.174	377	.404			
	Total	155.672	383				
Quality Consciousness	Between Groups	2.507	6	.418	1.147	.334	NS
	Within Groups	137.333	377	.364			
	Total	139.839	383				
Price Consciousness	Between Groups	2.653	6	.442	1.069	.380	NS
	Within Groups	155.909	377	.414			
	Total	158.562	383				
Information Utilization	Between Groups	2.014	6	.336	.696	.653	NS
	Within Groups	181.776	377	.482			
	Total	183.790	383				
Consumer Innovativeness and ethnocentrism	Between Groups	1.259	6	.210	.441	.851	NS
	Within Groups	179.418	377	.476			
	Total	180.677	383				

From the table, it can be inferred that the purchase decision factors do not have significant difference with type of branded clothes chosen by women

Conclusion:

Consumer purchase decision towards branded apparel has been studied. However, fashion is always seeking newness and uniqueness, consumer were found more self-expressive than following fashion. Fast and slow fashion consumers seek product conform to their self-image, however there were differences in terms of utilitarianism concept. Consumer involvement level should be considered by manufacturers and sellers as it influences purchase decision making.

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